

Title: Unlocking Ghana's Agricultural Potential: A 24-Hour Economy Approach

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Abstract:

This paper proposes a 24-hour economy approach to transform Ghana's agricultural sector, increasing productivity, efficiency, and revenue. By adopting double shift jobs and leveraging technology, the sector can meet growing demand, enhance value addition, and contribute to economic growth.

Introduction:

Ghana's agricultural sector faces challenges, including low productivity, limited irrigation, inadequate storage, and limited access to finance. A 24-hour economy approach can address these challenges, promoting a culture of extended working hours, improved productivity, and enhanced economic performance.

Demand for Agricultural Goods:

The market demand for fruits and vegetables in Ghana is growing at an annual rate of 10% (1). The agriculture market in Ghana is estimated to be worth \$3.40 billion in 2024 and is expected to grow to \$3.87 billion by 2029 (1).

Double Shift Jobs Integration:

To integrate double shift jobs into the logic frame for a 24-hour economy in the agricultural value chain, consider the following adjustments: Inputs, Process, Outputs, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Assumptions, and External Factors.

Benefits:

Increased production, efficiency, and revenue

Improved yield and quality of produce

Enhanced value addition and processing

Timely delivery and customer satisfaction

Job creation and economic growth

Conclusion:

A 24-hour economy approach in Ghana's agricultural sector can unlock its potential, meeting growing demand, enhancing value addition, and contributing to economic growth. By adopting double shift jobs and leveraging technology, the sector can become a driver of economic development.

References:

(1) "Agriculture in Ghana - Sector Growth & Industry Statistics", 2023

(2) Simon Moulds, "Ghana's agriculture sector: challenges and opportunities", 2022